

A STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL HOMONYMY AND POLYSEMY IN CORPUS LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. The article discusses the issue of distinguishing phraseological homonymy and polysemy in corpus linguistics and eliminating the semantic ambiguity that may arise in semantic analysis, and clarifying the meaning diversity of polysemous and homonymic phrases. The fact that the semantic diversity of homophrases cannot be completely eliminated by the filter of grammatical forms is justified by examples. The semantics of ambiguous expressions is analyzed based on syntactic framework.

Key words: Linguistic corpus, semantic analysis, phraseological polysemy, homonymy, phrase, homophrase, syntactic framework, grammatical filter, linguistic model.

Phraseology as a separate branch of linguistics emerged in Russian linguistics at the beginning of the 20th century. A.A. Potebnya, A. Shakhmatov contributed a lot to the formation of this branch, while in Uzbek linguistics it is possible to get a lot of information about this field of study through the research of a number of scientists such as Sh. Rahmatullayev, U. Tursunov, I. Kochkortoyev, G. Salomov; and in the years of independence scientists such as A. Mamatov, Sh. Usmonova, M. Kholikova, K. Bozorboyev.

The phenomenon of phraseological polysemy and homonymy, which occurs as a result of the formal uniformity and semantic diversity between idioms, is one of the topics waiting for a special research in our linguistics. In particular, it is extremely important to distinguish these two phenomena and sort out the issues around them in corpus linguistics.

The ability to express more than one meaning or the embodiment of different meanings in exactly one form is characteristic of all levels of linguistics, including phrases. However, in polysemy expressions, as in lexical polysemy, there is a distinction between original and derivative meanings. In lexical polysemy, the main, original meaning is equal to the correct meaning, and the derived meaning is equal to the displacement; in phraseological polysemy, in contrast, a phraseological unit does not have its own meaning, because any phraseological unit arises through the transfer of meaning. [Rakhmatullayev Sh. 1970; 5.]

Phraseological homonymy occurs due to the phenomenon of breaking the meaning-related connection between two expressions and becoming equal in form. Formation of homonymous phrases lexically occurs in 2 different ways:

a) one unit of the phrase is a homonym, and the other one is the same word; b) each unit of the phrase shown as a homonym is the same word. [Rakhmatullayev Sh. 1970; 7.] An example of the initial state is the expression *"to cut one's breath"* (literal translation from Uzbek). I. *Not allowing to speak, not raising one's voice.* II. *"Eliminating the upcoming force"*. Phraseological homonymy is formed through the homonymy of the word "breath" in this phrase.

In the second case, The expression *"to give one's answer"* (literal translation) could be an example: I. *To answer.* II. *To drive somebody out of somewhere.* III. *To give one's blessing, to betroth.* There is no homonymous lexeme in this phrase. However, in the case of a combination, three types of homonymy are formed.

It is extremely important for the development of the field to introduce phraseological polysemy and homonymy to the Uzbek corpus system, distinguish them, and eliminate semantic diversity and formal identity, which may arise from this. Because the transfer of phraseological units to the corpus causes a number of problems in all languages. These include cases where phraseological units are equal to their meaning, and the structure acquires a polysemic or homonymous character in the case of a phrase. For example, if we pay attention to the phrase *"hang around the neck"* (literal translation), this phrase has both its original meaning (to wear a medal or something similar around the neck) and several figurative meanings (1.

Put the blame on someone. 2. To prove one guilty and make them confess. 3. Make someone agree to undertake a task). Naturally, this causes a number of inconveniences when introducing the language into the electronic system. Because the models based on grammatical forms, which help to distinguish lexical homonyms and polysemy in corpus linguistics, do not work at the phraseological level. In this case, it is necessary to develop linguistic models based on semantic analysis and syntactic structure in order to be able to automatically distinguish polysemous and similar expressions in the text. We will try to distinguish the semantic diversity of the above phrase *"hang around the neck"* on this basis:

The concrete noun + grammatical form ensures that the expression is used as its main meaning (to wear a medal or something similar around the neck).

The abstract noun + grammatical form ensures that the expression is used figuratively, meaning *"making one confess or proving one guilty"*.

A noun depicting action or process + grammatical form ensures that the expression is used to convey the meaning *"persuading one to undertake a task"*

It is difficult to "introduce" the phrase *"raise one's hand"* which has acquired a homonymic meaning, to the electronic system even on the basis of the above mentioned syntactic framework. Because it is equivalent to the compound in its original meaning (*to literally raise one's hand up*) and also creates phraseological homonymy (I. *To hit*. II. *To favor someone*. III. *To surrender*) The same phrase could also be used as *"to raise one's hand for somebody or something"* and all of its semantic potential could be shown through this form of the phrase. The meaning of such a phrase in the text can be specified only by adding semantic keywords for each form to the corpus system. It seems that different linguistic models need to be developed in order to fully incorporate homonymy and polysemy in phrases into the corpus system, because the meanings of phrases are so identical and so diverse that it cannot be integrated into an electronic system. It also makes the process of automatic translation extremely difficult for non-Uzbek speakers.

Therefore, it is an urgent task of ours to differentiate and eliminate the phraseological similarity and ambiguity in the electronic database of the Uzbek language. Through this, the complete formation of the Uzbek corpus can be achieved.

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